

HOW SCHOOL PROJECTS HAVE NEGATIVELY IMPACTED LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the issue of how school projects have negatively impacted student learning, precisely because of their design, which does not address social issues in a categorized way and does not present a problem situation that represents a teaching challenge to the student. This premeditated and announced failure is associated with the fact that, since the student and the teacher do not know what they want to explore, each one intends to be working on the development of the so-called project. What we end up with is a student who did not investigate what he or she should have, due to the teacher's lack of guidance and lack of transparency in his or her guiding objective, and a teacher who reports that he or she gave the student all the space and time necessary to investigate his or her topics and add them to the results. What can be understood is the confusion that exists regarding what constitutes a research project, with its strict technical standards, and Project Pedagogy, with its specific teaching doctrine. The way it has been applied in educational settings, neither one thing nor the other is achieved, and the results are always a didactic -pedagogical cheating. This is a bibliographical essay, based on the author's pedagogical practice. What needs to be done immediately is for schools and teachers to understand the dimension of a project and its applicability as a didactic element; to do this, it is necessary to understand what didactics is and to be very clear about what the objectives are in relation to learning, to know the level of intellectuality of students, their predisposition to learn, the availability of books and opportunities for empirical situations to develop experiences and the proportion of teachers' knowledge in relation to the projects they develop, the problems that involve them, the problem situation to be solved or explored in

depth, the human and material resources available, deadlines for execution, evaluation, aggregation of information.

Keywords: Educational projects. Project pedagogy. Essay. Didactics. Interdisciplinarity.

INTRODUCTION

Projects are proposals for studies of problems posed by society to scientists and academics, with the intention of achieving greater knowledge about the problems and, at the same time, presenting a possible and viable solution. They have no intention whatsoever of being an educational proposal or of personological construction, although they can be transformed into one, according to the opportunities for knowledge and didactic application. Therefore, projects are, strictly speaking, scientific instruments, determinants of planned actions, with defined deadlines for their execution and completion. After this moment, what we have are systematic studies applied to the results achieved and the details revealed by the investigation, at which point it becomes didactic and, subsequently, a plan is drawn up, containing methods of action on the problem, aiming at its complete solution or that it can be alleviated through didactic or pedagogical intervention.

Due to their strictly scientific nature, projects require a transparent problem situation that guides their aims to increase and expand knowledge about the target object of investigation. This defines what is actually intended to be achieved through systematic research and what response will be obtained by the general public and the academic community upon completion of the study.

It can be said that a project is strictly didactic, given its perspicacity in keeping the researcher focused on the details that are added to the thought, as he delves deeper into the analysis of the data and the results obtained. Paradoxically, it does not always prove to be pedagogical, because its interest can be so particular that it ignores the whole, the integrality of the atomic principle itself, which causes its *sui generis role to be confused* with the role of Pedagogy.

Due to this condition of cognitive, epistemological and empirical misunderstanding regarding the didactic and investigative dimension of a project, many teachers, guided by supposed theorists in the area of education and related areas, have been indiscriminately applying the famous *projects* in regular basic education schools, as if this were a didactic and pedagogical revolution and were capable of promoting authentic miracles in learning,

considering that, through their implementation, students were in direct contact with reality, learning through experiences.

Theoretically, this is a true condition; because the student, together with his classmates, would outline clear objectives regarding a given theme or object of study, seeking to know, in depth, the psychology of this object and the more they gained cognitive power over it, the more potential they would have to elaborate complex and dynamic questions, finding and defining the links that permeate them and build their structure. However, empirically, all this reveals itself to be a delusional assumption and a latent desire, which thus persists *ad infinitum*, precisely because the way in which it is elaborated is carried out in order to fulfill a pedagogical task of the school, a challenge of goals that is part of the formal curricular dictate and not as a way to compensate for or even extend the short space of time that the student and teacher have to teach and learn, respectively.

The failure of the project is already determined in its elaboration, in which the creator and executor of the same, clarifying, the teacher, does not seek to carry out a prior situational study around the theme and/or problem that he intends to address, that is, he does not understand the problems surrounding the object that are affecting the population, how they interfere in the life and existence of individuals and the community and what they think about them, what they propose, empirically, as [*possible*] immediate and future solution.

From this preliminary investigation, carried out empirically with the intended target audience, a hypothesis is raised about the origin of the problem, its manifestation, direct and indirect impacts and possible solution, as well as the amount of knowledge that can be gained by participants through direct contact with the problem and its understanding, as well as legitimate actions of a cognitive nature, through the publication of the results and analyses of the study. This represents the moment in which the project takes on a strictly pedagogical character. This idea, raised from prior and superficial knowledge of the problem, can, at the end of the study, be proven or refuted.

The problem we have today is related to teacher training, both initial and continuing, in which we do not learn how to do scientific projects, much less about *Project Pedagogy*, which is an active methodology created by John Dewey (1859-1952) and continued by Kilpatrick (1871-1965). Knowing, in a short-sighted way, about both, what is practiced in regular elementary school is a proposal that does not meet the precepts of either, only filling empty spaces that could be taken towards relevant cognitive activities, accompanied by the teacher and dynamized towards learning.

THE DYNAMICS OF PROJECTS AT SCHOOL

In regular education, projects have become fashionable, driven by rule-makers and methodological fads, in which the aim is to promote advanced learning processes; however, without due knowledge of the technique and without the methodological rigor that it demands, what we end up with is something devoid of causal connection with objective reality and, to the same extent, with subjective reality, because neither the student nor their teacher really know what they are trying to understand.

A tangle of ideas is created about something that is in vogue in the media and applied as a project, without an exact description of the epistemic dimension of the object, without clarifying the theoretical bases on which the research is intended to be based. The steps that will be taken in the execution are not described, such as the collection of theoretical data, the collection of empirical data (interviews, *on-site visits*, participant observation, meetings between team members, workshops, partial presentation of results, discussion of deviations from the objectives).

The problem begins with the presentation of the proposal to work with projects, which simply states that, when applying learning processes using projects as a methodology, the student absorbs much more, because he/she experiences the situation empirically, having direct contact with the object and its transformations, once subjected to manipulation. This is an idea that comes close to the truth [*no more than that*]; because, when considering that learning actually happens in a broader, deeper and more lasting way, when the student has access to experience, especially when performing the task, this condition cannot be limited to the practice itself; he/she must know in advance what he/she is going to do and the result may come as a surprise to him/her; but he/she cannot be allowed to interpret it according to his/her limited knowledge of cause and effect regarding the phenomenon.

Francis Bacon (2000) is categorical in arguing that no intelligence is self-sufficient to the point of self-determination and, if left to its own condition of phenomenological analysis and interpretation of things, ends up creating chimeras and other oddities that are given as logical interpretation. Thus, all experience must be coordinated within precepts that know the directions and in which direction one is advancing to the detriment of new knowledge or phenomenological understanding.

The teacher presents his project proposal and, once approved, it is applied to the students and they are left *to* develop it, without knowing what to actually do; but this is what interests them least, considering that the ideal is to pretend that they are developing something great and

of great relevance to science (sic). In the meantime, the coordinator of the supposed project is left to his own inertia, leaving the students to discover, through his protagonism (sic) the things that interest him and that are linked to his investigative studies.

For some supposed wise men in the field of education who defend learning through projects, the teacher's non-intervention is the most correct measure that can be taken and the teaching method to be applied, because his interference would hinder the discovery and reading of the world that the student has the rare opportunity to do. Without knowing that he is acting in this way and which philosophical doctrine he is applying, this individual is defending Platonism, the failed idea that all knowledge is innate, and that it is enough for the human being to come into contact with phenomenological situations for it to manifest itself spontaneously. Plato tries to prove this theory, based on his own ignorance and the prejudice he had towards the servants of aristocratic families.

As a consequence of this process, school projects have the sole mission of disrupting the teaching-pedagogical process, because in their name, the teacher does not teach his regular classes, nor do the students participate in them when, by chance, he decides to present something. Unsatisfied, the students begin to ask to be absent from classes in other subjects, always in the name of the infamous project. As a result, these so-called *educational projects* do not serve to improve the teacher's knowledge or to promote effective learning among students, because they spend all their time pursuing something they do not understand, nor do they know enough to carry out an investigative project or a learning strategy using a project methodology.

THE SUBTLE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN PROJECT AND PROJECT PEDAGOGY

A project is a rigid structure, designed to guide thought in a proposed direction, *a priori*, whose objective is to discover something new, expand the level of knowledge and/or shed light on something that, at first glance, is not properly clarified, to the point of arousing controversy when analyzed and interpreted. It is divided into chains of thought, where each stage defines exactly the step to be taken by the researcher, and must respond to questions and also validate and/or refute the idea presented in its scope. It is coordinated by the clear and broad approach to a problem, collected in the social environment and supported by a question, which represents the *leitmotiv* of the situation.

Throughout the development of the research, many objects emerge, as part of the exploration of the target object of studies, showing themselves to be linked to it in a more or less objective way and, given the fundamental characteristic of their aspects, the analyses and

interpretations of them are deepened, in an attempt to know and/or clarify their contributions to the occurrence and support of the phenomenon.

None of these actions are discussed together, except with the research partners themselves or with the project supervisor [*if applicable*], and everything is presented at the end of the work, through a thesis, a conclusive set of everything that was studied and discovered during the research effort. Likewise, there is no evaluation of the project, namely whether the objectives were achieved or not and, to what didactic proportions, exactly, because, in the end, it is not the project that is presented as the object of judgment, but rather the results of the research carried out.

Based on this condition of methodological and didactic rigor to which projects are linked, John Dewey (1859-1952) developed a teaching methodology that was based on the structure of the projects and not on them, enabling the creation of a pedagogical structure for learning; Project Pedagogy was created, uniting the classical Greek thought of interest in the integral formation of man [*a principle very dear to Pedagogy*], and all the possibility of discoveries arising from the advancement of thought on the creation of hypotheses and analyses and interpretations of the stages of project development.

In Project Pedagogy, each structuring part of the project is duly scrutinized, analyzed, interpreted and discussed to exhaustion until each finding is understood and how it relates to the object, influencing the situations and mechanisms of action and interaction, because the interest is that the student is able to understand the whole based on the understanding of the parts.

It should be clarified that, “Project Pedagogy arose from the need to develop a pedagogical work methodology, which had as its goal the valorization of the participation of the student and the educator in the learning-teaching process, considering that learning takes precedence over teaching, making them directly responsible for the elaboration and development of each Work Project; consequently, they would become capable of acting freely in their daily lives, enabling them to make decisions autonomously” (Souza et al, 2013, p. 288).

The goal of Project Pedagogy is to enable broad and unrestricted discussion between the whole and the parts, so that at the end of the activity all those involved have expanded their analytical and interpretative context. Unlike projects, the knowledge acquired in these stages is subjected to rigorous evaluation, aiming at the consolidation of what was studied and discovered in the theoretical and empirical deepening. At the end, the conclusion is discussed among peers, in order to carry out symbolic exchanges on the understanding of the process, as a whole. In a scientific project, there is no such particular type of didactic-pedagogical

intervention, in which the final product is presented to the general public, in the form of a thesis, which will be judged by those who read it and, from there, the appropriate criticisms will be elaborated, understanding these as open questions that aim to clarify the subject and the answer presented to the problem that theoretically and/or empirically grounds it.

This way of taking the results arising from discoveries, amid research that is developed through previously defined contexts, amid a project, where everyone participates in the search for solutions, allows thinking to go from the whole to the parts and from the parts to the whole, following the principle of complexity theory, providing knowledge and intellectual development in a comprehensive and connected way, enabling symbolic exchanges in real time, both through mechanisms of theoretical appropriation and through empirical means, experimenting with situations and even reproducing some phenomena.

One of the advantages of this learning system is that thinking is organized by the linear description of what was planned, presenting students with a step-by-step guide to developing an idea until it becomes knowledge, including peer evaluation, interpretation by others, and judgment regarding its value and even its applicability to empirical situations. This is a didactic-pedagogical work that must be directly aligned with the practice of each teacher who decides to use this learning method, which requires knowledge of the methodology on their part and, in addition, they need to discuss their proposal with teachers from other areas/disciplines in order to verify whether there is the possibility of an interdisciplinary overlap in the process.

Therefore, the ideal would be for the entire school to seek to be part of these projects, because this would give students a broader idea of the temporality of facts, the geography of phenomena, human or non-human influences on their occurrence and in what dimension it presents itself and how it can be mitigated, reduced or whether it is inherent to the entire mechanical process involving its physical manifestation. The aim is to create mechanisms for the factual interpretation of phenomenological reality and, with this, improve intelligence, creating conditions for creativity. The tendency is for students to learn to write scientifically, to debate topics within technical standards, to conduct theoretical research based on their objectives, obeying the didactic parameters of temporality and objective distance from the target object of study and, finally, to know and recognize the psychology of the object as *the leitmotif* of their scientific interactions.

This process must be addressed by all those involved in the learning process, because in Project Pedagogy, the teaching condition is not clear in the prominent figure of the teacher, since both the students and the teacher will be crossed by the discoveries arising from their empirical investigations, which may prove to be innovative for all those involved, considering

that what will dictate the direction of learning is the research and no longer the individuals, with the latter being responsible for the analysis of the facts, the phenomena, their interpretation and, *a posteriori*, the production of the synthesis.

Contrary to this, as schools have been carrying out their projects, each student writes something that they name and register with the name of *a project*, leaving students to drift [literally] from then on and, to make matters worse, what they discover is not subjected to heavy scrutiny under the principle of falsifiability, leaving them with the impression that they have advanced in the *vortex* of knowledge, when what they have added is nothing more than information that, without rigorous analysis, is nothing more than *useless knowledge*. The main interest with Project Pedagogy is the creation of a space for empirical contact with science, with facts and phenomena and their possibilities of occurrence in physical space and time, what is conventionally called seasonality, the influence of intrinsic and extrinsic factors on each situation itself and how one can intervene to find a viable and safe solution, in every sense.

If not applied in this way, all pedagogical work loses its meaning, because didactics are absent and, if the proposal of Pedagogy is the integral formation of man, without a didactic direction applied to this idea, that is, a balance between what is learned and what is foreseen as teaching, there is a mere application of old outdated formulas that prove to be efficient and ineffective because of the lack of technical rigor and scientific discipline.

CONCLUSION

In this essay, we sought to discuss the issue of how scientific projects and Project Pedagogy ended up being confused in the educational environment and this led to a state of chaos in their application as learning strategies, in which, instead of promoting such a condition, it has reduced any possibilities of expanding it, because the teacher, without knowing what to do, reproduces on paper any idea that is dominating his thinking and that he believes can help students become more intelligent and capable of understanding reality.

In the absence of an in-depth study that clarifies the problem that is believed to be plausible, it is not possible to develop a project, much less propose a learning methodology based on Project Pedagogy, because it is assumed that there is a need for broad, compelling investigations that enable progress in the structuring of scientific thought, in which the discussion about such discoveries provides a glimpse of new scientific and didactic opportunities.

Projects have a scientific dimension, making it clear that their purpose is to guide an investigation with very objective ends, aiming to solve a strict problem, generally of a social nature and even if it is particular, its intent extends to the general population, unlike what we have with Project Pedagogy, in which its purpose is to construct a didactic thought, expanding the condition of phenomenological knowledge about and from facts. It is necessary for the teacher to be clear about this, so that, when proposing the elaboration of such pedagogical practices, he can direct the student and the results of his investigation towards a sense of expanding his knowledge, subjecting them to the principle of falsifiability, understanding that what he discovers may not be representing a fact about his target object of study, there being many things to be considered, especially the anthropological and sociological aspects pertinent to them, together with consideration of the psychology of the object.

The objectives of the projects used as teaching resources are to create interdisciplinary learning mechanisms within school spaces, involving students in synchronous searches for knowledge based on empirical situations. Everything possible to achieve an unparalleled achievement in the production of ideas and development of critical sense applied to science, as long as the application of the technique is directed towards the proposed end, which is to bring the student and teacher closer to the maximum potential for acquiring new questions, understanding that phenomena occur in different ways and have different behaviors depending on where they occur, due to the influence of geographic and also human nature (political and economic).

What needs to be done is for the school and teachers to understand the dimension of a project and its applicability as a didactic element; to do this, it is necessary to understand what didactics is and to be very clear about what the objectives are in relation to learning, to know the level of intellectuality of the students, their predisposition to learn, the availability of books and opportunities for empirical situations to develop experiences and the proportion of the teachers' knowledge in relation to the projects they develop, the problems that involve them, the problem situation to be resolved or explored in depth, the human and material resources available, deadlines for execution, evaluation, aggregation of information.

Carried out outside this epistemic and didactic scope, what we have is nothing more than the consumption of time towards nothing, believing in the *ex nihilo condition* as a form of learning, and this is a condition that completely escapes the scope of education as a mechanism for the formation of human integrity through the acquisition and interpretation of knowledge and understanding.

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